

Dental Crowding

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A twenty three year old female patient reported to the dental clinic with a chief complaint of irregular upper and lower front teeth. Intraorally the patient had Class I molar and canine relationship with moderate to severe crowding and proclination in upper and lower anterior teeth. The patient was skeletal Class I with horizontal growth pattern. The patient was treated with comprehensive fixed mechanotherapy, with all first premolar extractions, with conventional metal brackets having 0.022" slot. The leveling and alignment of the teeth took about 9 months with the correction of anterior crowding in upper and lower anterior teeth. The extractions were done prior to the leveling and alignment stage so that about half of the space was utilized before the space closure stage. The space closure was done on U/L 19X25 SS archwires and it took about 6 months. The total treatment took about 1.5 years. Upper and lower Hawley's retainers were given after the completion of treatment.

Extra-oral Photographs (Pre-Treatment)

Frontal View

Smiling View

Profile View

Intra-oral Photographs (Pre-Treatment)

Right Lateral

Left Lateral

Frontal View

Maxillary Occlusal

Mandibular Occlusal

OPG (Orthopantomogram)

Lateral Cephalogram

Extra-oral Photographs (Post Treatment)

Frontal View

Left Lateral

Right Lateral

Intra-oral Photographs (Post-Treatment)

Right Lateral

Left Lateral

Frontal View

Maxillary Occlusal

Mandibular Occlusal

OPG (Orthopantomogram)

Lateral Cephalogram